

Henning E. Jørgensen in Memoriam

September 2025 - Erik Høg, associate professor emeritus, Copenhagen University, Niels Bohr Institute

Henning Elo Jørgensen was born on January 16, 1938, and passed away after a few days of illness on November 23, 2010, but many of us still remember him as a unifying figure at the Astronomical Observatory for many years. It has long bothered me that nothing can be found about Henning when you search the internet, no obituary or other mention, even though he meant so much to us for a long time.

Figure 1. Henning at the observatory as a student in 1960 with an electromechanical calculator, a standard equipment for an astronomer at that time. – Photo from Jørgen Otzen Petersen.

Henning graduated from Nykøbing Cathedral School on the Danish island Falster in 1956, the same school where I graduated in 1950. He studied mathematics, physics, chemistry and astronomy at the University of Copenhagen from 1956 and became a 'cand. mag et mag. scient.' with astronomy as a major in 1963. Henning was employed at the University of Copenhagen in 1965, was given an office at Østervold Observatory of Copenhagen University and was appointed professor of 'astronomy with a special focus on astrophysics' in 1982. He taught and researched astrophysics with a special interest first in stellar physics and later in galaxies and cosmology and wrote textbooks for teaching. He is an author and co-author of scientific publications in the period 1967-2008.

Henning was director of the Astronomical Observatory at the University of Copenhagen for several periods from ca. 1974 to 2005. In that year, astronomy as a part of physics was incorporated into the Niels Bohr Institute, thus ending a 363-year era that began in 1642 with the inauguration of the Observatory at the Round Tower. Henning was always the one you could talk to about tasks, problems or good news. I could always rely on him in my work with the astrometry satellites and with China in the eighties.

He represented the Observatory in many contexts: In the Faculty of Science, where he was dean for a period, and for many years he was the Danish representative in the International Scientific Committee (CCI) for the observatories in the Canary Islands – i.e. the international board of the observatories on La Palma and Tenerife. It was the board behind the Roque de Los Muchachos Observatory, where the Carlsberg Meridian Circle from Brorfelde and the Nordic Optical Telescope (NOT) were set up. He was a member of the board of the European Southern Observatory (ESO Council), where he was involved in the work on the construction of the world's largest optical telescope, the Very Large Telescope (VLT) of 4x8.2 m, which was decided on 8 December 1987. He was a member of the board of the Tycho Brahe Planetarium.

We remember Henning as a friendly and always welcoming person.

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